

"LEARNING THE TALENT"

Abduxakim Nigmatovich Abdullayev

Tashkent State Pedagogical University, Department of "Technological Education Methodology", assistant professor, Tashkent city.

abdullayeva.abduhakim.1967@gmail.com

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ANNOTATION: Beams are among the simplest suspension lifting mechanisms. They are used for assembling and disassembling various devices, for transporting and lifting goods in workshops. Three-legged and one-legged poles and suspension ways are used to hang the poles.

KEY WORDS: wire, simple suspension, lifting mechanism, lever, pinion, power source, electric, pneumatic, wire structure, wheel, brake, Chain, Friction surfaces of the brake, Planetary gear transmission, load chain.

RESULTS:

Table of records of the laboratory work "Learning the language".

The studied parameters				
T / r	Name	Designation	Unit of measure	Value
1	2	3	4	5
Initial information				
1	Load capacity	Q	t	1,0
2	Multiplicity of ordinary polyspast	U_n	-	2
3	Chain wire diameter	d	mm	11
O'lchash natijalari				
1	Worm gear center distance	a_w	mm	
2	Number of cargo star slots	Z	piece	
3	The number of entries of the worm	Z_1	piece	
4	The number of teeth on the worm wheel	Z_2	piece	
5	Chervyak's step	r	mm	
6	The diameter of the starting circle of the traction star	D_t	mm	
7	Brake friction surface outer diameter	D_1	mm	
8	Inner diameter of brake friction surface	D_2	mm	
9	The number of pairs of brake friction surfaces	a	piece	

Calculation results				
1	Gear number of worm gear	U		
2	Torque on the load star shaft	T_{yuk}	N·mm	
3	The diameter of the starting circle of the load star	D_b	mm	
4	Torque on the worm shaft when lifting the load	T_{ch}	N·mm	
5	Torque on the worm shaft when unloading	T'_u	N·mm	
6	Braking torque	T_t	N·mm	
7	Reading power in a worm	S	N	
8	Average brake friction radius	$r_o'r$	mm	
9	Reserve coefficient of braking	K_t		

DISCUSSION:

According to the design of the mechanism, there are worm and gear wheels, and according to the type of movement source - lever, electric and pneumatic wheels. Fig. 1 shows the construction of a worm wheel with a handle. Its main transmission mechanism consists of a pair of worms. The worm-3 receives the rotational motion from the drive chain-1 thrown through the drive sprocket and transmits it to the worm wheel. Chain-1 is manually operated. The worm wheel is made together with the load-pulling star-5, when it rotates, the pull-chain-7 fixed to the frame body is wound or loosened, as a result of which the load hanging on the hook-9 rises or falls. Brake-8 serves to stop the load at the required height.

Load-bearing (load-pulling) brakes (Fig. 3) are used more frequently in lever-type machines, where the friction working surfaces come together under the influence of the weight of the load. When the asterisk-2 is stopped from rotating through the chain-1, due to the opposite effect of the load hanging on the hook, the rotating moment is directed in the opposite direction on the worm-2 shaft, which, in turn, brings the frictional surfaces of the brake-8 together. creates a connecting axial force S . The load is held in a suspended position even when the chain-1 is released after the friction surfaces of the brake are connected. An external force is again applied to chain-1 to lower or raise the load again. Load-bearing brakes provide smooth stopping of a load at any distance at the same acceleration. The useful work coefficient (F.I.K.) of wormwood is usually equal to 0.6...0.7. In order to increase it as much as

possible, the worm transmission is made non-self-braking, that is, the angle of elevation of the worm screw line is taken to be around $16...20^\circ$. The load capacity of the worm conveyors can be $1...10t$, the lifting speed can be $0.56...0.11$ m/min, while the speed of the driving chain is 3.0 m/min. Coefficient efficiency factor of gears with planetary gears is relatively high ($0.7...0.8$), compact in design, but less load-bearing. In particular, when the lifting speed is $1.3...0.2$ m/min, it lifts a load with a mass of 0.5 to 4 tons.

Figure 1. General view of a willow with a worm on the handle

1st drive working chain, 2nd drive sprocket,
3-worm, 4-worm wheel, 5-loading star, 6-hanging hook,
7-load traction chain, 8-disc brake, 9-load hook.

Figure 2. The scheme of the handle worm wheel

1-drive chain, 2-drive sprocket, 3 - Z1 worm, 4-worm wheel, 5-load traction star, 6-body, 7-rope suspension hook, 8-disc load-support brake, 9-load traction

chain, 10-load hook suspension; 11-load hook; Q is the mass of the load to be lifted.

Figure 3. Scheme of load-support brake with constant pressure and braking torque. 1-case-bearing, 2-brake cup (snap), 3-nut, 4-spring, 5-axle, 6-holder (screw) on the runner, 7-holder (screw), drive worm shaft, 9 and 10-friction (friction) disks, 11-pin, S-reading force compressing friction surfaces.

Figure 3.

When working with Tal, the following basic safety requirements must be met:

1. It is allowed to work with a valid machine that has been registered with the bodies of the State Technical Control Committee and has undergone regular technical inspection.
2. Persons who have been trained in safety techniques are allowed to work.
3. When hanging, it is necessary to fix it securely.
4. It is forbidden to carry a load with a mass exceeding that specified in the passport.
5. Do not stand under the raised load.
6. Cargo lashing ropes and load securing devices must be serviceable and periodically inspected.

CONCLUSION:

The purpose of the laboratory work is to get acquainted with the structure and operation of wormwood, and to learn to study its other parameters using the given initial parameters.

The following initial parameters are given:

- load carrying capacity of the beam $Q = 1t$;

- multiplicity of tal simple hoist $U_n = 2$;
- the diameter of the steel wire in the rings of the load chain made by welding $d = 11$ mm.

Order of work

1. Tal is divided into parts.
2. The diagram of the beam and the sketch of the load-support brake (in clipping) are drawn.
3. The following parameters are determined by measuring or counting and are determined in the circuit diagram:

a - center-to-center distance of the worm gear, mm;

Z - the number of slots of the load star;

Z_1 - the number of worms;

Z_2 - the number of teeth of the worm wheel;

r - the reading step of the worm, mm;

D_t is the diameter of the starting circle of the traction star (the diameter of the middle of the chain rings);

D_2 - internal diameter of disc brake friction surfaces, mm;

D_1 - outer diameter of disc brake friction surfaces, mm.

4. The blade is reassembled and tested for performance.

5. The number of transmissions of the worm gear is determined:

$$U = \frac{Z_2}{Z_1}$$

6. In the case of lifting the load, the torque generated on the star shaft of

$$T_{\text{cargo}} = \frac{Q D_6}{2U_n \eta \eta_n}, \text{ N}\cdot\text{mm}$$

the load is determined:

where Q is cargo mass, kg; U_n - polypast multiplicity; $\eta = 0.94$ - Coefficient efficiency factor of the load star; $\eta_n = 0.975$ - Coefficient efficiency factor of ordinary polyspast; D_b is the diameter of the starting circle of the load star,

which is determined by the following formula:
$$D_6 = \sqrt{\left(\frac{t}{\sin \frac{90^\circ}{Z}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{d}{\cos \frac{90^\circ}{Z}}\right)^2}$$

where t is the inner length of the chain ring, t = 31mm is accepted when d = 11mm.

7. The torque applied to the worm shaft when lifting the load is determined:

$$T = \frac{T_{\text{cargo}}}{U \eta}$$

where T_{yuk} is the torque on the load star shaft in the lifting state, N·mm, the transmission number of the U-worm gear; $\eta_{\text{ch}} \approx 0.75$ is the FIK of the worm gear when the worm is the guide.

8. The torque created by the weight of the load and delivered to the brake shaft

$$T = \frac{T_{\text{cargo}} \eta'}{U}, \text{ N}\cdot\text{mm}$$

in the lowering position is determined:

where ≈ 0.5 is the FIK of the worm wheel driving part of the worm gear.

9. Braking torque is determined: $T_t = s.a.f$, N·mm

where S is the reading force compressing the disk on the brake shaft, it is found

$$S = \frac{2T}{d_2},$$

by the following formula: N

where d_2 is the pitch diameter of the worm wheel, mm: $d_2 = z_2 m$;

m - communication module, mm: $m = \frac{p}{\pi}$,

$a = 2$ - number of pairs of friction surfaces; r_{or} - the average radius of friction

$$r = \frac{D_1 + D_2}{4};$$

between the disk and the screw, mm;

f - the coefficient of friction between the brake discs, $f = 0.35$ is taken when the friction surfaces of the discs consist of steel and brake tape.

10. The necessary torque on the worm shaft to unload the load is determined: $T_o = T_t - T_{to}$, N·mm

11. The reserve coefficient of braking is determined: $K_m = \frac{T_m}{T_{mo}}$

12. The force applied to the traction chain to lift the load is determined:

$$P_n = \frac{2 \cdot T}{D_T \cdot U_n \cdot n \cdot \varphi}, \text{ N}$$

where n is the number of workers, it can be assumed that $n = 1$ and 2 ; $\varphi = 0.8$ is a coefficient that takes into account that when several people work together, the force is not applied to the lever at the same time.

13. The necessary force in lowering the load R_o is determined:

$$P_o = \frac{2 \cdot T_o}{D_T \cdot U_n \cdot n \cdot \varphi} , N$$

14. The results of the laboratory work are recorded in the record table and relevant conclusions are drawn.

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